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DESIGN EPISTEMOLOGY: WEDDING REASON + REVELATION

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ABSTRACT

Although the foundation for any discipline is how its practitioners know, design is still uncertain about its epistemology. Design is not alone in this. Science and theology have debated epistemological questions within and between themselves for decades. Within that debate emerged common ground in critical realism, a philosophy that combines cognizance of external reality with assent to the power that personal perspectives exert over our perceptions (Barbour, 1974; Polkinghorne, 1998). Michael Polanyi's epistemology of personal knowledge is based on critical realism (Polanyi, 1958).

This paper proposes that epistemology grounded in personal knowledge might serve as a model for a design epistemology called Reason + Revelation, that can integrate design as craft with design as science, illuminate how designers combine intuition and analysis, inform how design education can move from tacit to explicit knowledge, and suggest a distinctive design research methodology that blends qualitative and quantitative methods.

Keywords:
epistemology, knowledge, design thinking

OVERVIEW: WAYS OF KNOWING

"Reason and revelation, the two conceivable sources of knowledge."
Edward O. Wilson, *Consilience* (1998, p. 35)

The foundation for any discipline is how its practitioners know. Design, a young and growing discipline, is still afloat on a sea of uncertainty about how designers know. Do we think designerly thoughts in designerly ways distinct from other disciplines? Do we come to know logically like scientists or intuitively like artists? Does design knowledge come through

reason or revelation? These are some of the open epistemological questions upon which design academics, and design thinkers, continue to float.

A brief account of recent epistemological argumentation broadly, and its analogies in design, will help frame the question. Epistemology touches the very foundations of thought. 'Is there something there' is at ground level. Without answering in detail, it's sufficient to say that people act as though there is a reality external to them. Noted physicist John Polkinghorne says succinctly,

"Yet few critics of the ideas of truth and reality are so committed to that cause that it is a matter of indifference to them what kind of doctor, witch or medical, they consult when they are ill. Nor do they tend to regard belief in the safe functioning of the aircraft they are about to board as being sufficiently established if it has arisen simply as the result of a socially negotiated consensus" (Polkinghorne, 2005, p. 3).

In recent centuries positivism built on the belief in objective reality through rational study resulting in the methods of modern science. The modernist movement in design was an outgrowth of a positivists approach to knowing. But positivism, and modernism built upon it, fell into hard times in the 20th century with postmodernism's critique of objective study and the failure of scientific study to provide for deeper meaning beyond mechanics. A postmodern design dialogue in *Émigré* magazine and "Cranbrook Design: The New Discourse" reflected this shift. (McCoy & McCoy, 1990) With positivism being questioned, the epistemological discussion shifted from the study of objects and nature, to that of language. Klaus Krippendorff's proposed "Semantic Turn, A New Foundation for Design" relies on language and it's socially constructed meaning. (Krippendorff, 2006) As Krippendorff says, the criterion of a constructivist epistemology is viability (2006, p. 22): what works for

the community, resulting in a trend toward pragmatism. While pragmatism provides guidance for what: ‘do what works,’ it fails to give motive for why: ‘what ought we to do?’ But as Herbert Simon describes it, design is not so neutral, “the designer is concerned with how things *ought* to be - how they ought to be in order to attain goals” (Simon, 1996, p. 4).

Recent emphasis on design thinking in books by Tim Brown (Brown, 2009) and Roger Martin (Martin, 2009) beg for an answer to the question, how do designers come to know? Nigel Cross argued that designers have distinctive ways of knowing, saying “the underlying axiom of this discipline [design] is that there are forms of knowledge special to the awareness and ability of a designer...” (Cross, 2001, p. 54). In his book *The Sciences of the Artificial*, Herbert Simon recommended that design draw upon the methods of science (Simon, 1996). In his book *Educating the Reflective Practitioner*, Donald Schön has proposed an epistemology of design practice where designers know by doing, not from theoretical study (1987). Commenting on Simon and Schön, Alain Findeli said, “the distinction between methodological and epistemological realms is no longer necessary or even relevant” (Findeli, 2001, p. 10) suggesting design practice and epistemology are synonymous. Several authors have discussed whether design knowledge is more procedural, know-how like arts and crafts, or declarative like the sciences. Given the above, I think it’s safe to say there is no current consensus on how designers know, leaving a budding discipline with an unsatisfactory foundation and an unresolved epistemology. How can we frame an appropriate epistemology for design in the midst of these diverse trajectories of thought? I propose to sketch an epistemological approach for design that integrates some of the various threads of thought just described.

AN INTEGRATED EPISTEMOLOGY EXAMPLE: SCIENCE + THEOLOGY

There is historic precedent for an integrated epistemology. Since the enlightenment, science and religion epitomized the conflict between rival epistemologies. In the second half of the 20th century several voices sought to reconcile these differences. Ian Barbour, with his PhD in Physics from University of Chicago and a BDiv from Yale University, began to seriously examine the similarities between science

and theology. Barbour freely recognized that science’s “apparent objectivity contrasts with the subjectivity of religion” (Barbour, 1974, p. 2), yet he said, “I will try to show that science is not as objective, nor religion as subjective, as these two opposing schools of thought both assumed” (Barbour, 1974, pp. 5-6). He did this in part by showing how both science and religion utilize myths, models and paradigms as thinking tools. Parallel to this, scientist and philosopher Michael Polanyi had articulated that all scientific discoveries grow out of skills and habits handed down from one scientist to another and that scientific knowledge is traditional, i.e., handed down the same way. He demonstrated that scientists, like everyone else, tend to see what they are looking for and that acts of personal judgment are involved in assessment of experiments. Polanyi affirmed that “All human knowledge is personal knowledge” (Polanyi, 1958) emphasizing that scientists are persons with personal perspectives. Some years later, eminent physicist and theologian John Polkinghorne affirmed Polanyi’s personal knowledge (Polkinghorne, 1998, p. 17) and stated that “science is not just read out directly from nature but its progress involves creative acts by thinking minds” (1998, p. 16). Polkinghorne’s statement reflects that in the latter part of the 20th century many scientists had begun to widely acknowledge themselves as persons with interpretive viewpoints. Polkinghorne noted this in saying “all scientifically interesting facts are already interpreted facts” (1998, p. 9). Religion had been seen by many as a personal matter. Now science was seen as personal as well.

During the time scientists were questioning the possibility of objectivity, the study of theology had also been changing by employing more scientific methods. Beginning in the 19th century, Christian theology began to interpret scripture by reexamination of historical contexts in light of archeology, through form criticism based on literary theory and text analysis, and by hermeneutical processes forming a ‘science of interpretation.’ These brought a distinctively scientific flavor to Christian theological studies.

With the position of the objective observer effectively discredited in science, and the use of scientific methods in theology, intellectual space

was cleared to propose an integrated means of knowing for science and theology.

CRITICAL REALISM

In Ian Barbour's book "Myths, Models and Paradigms: A Comparative Study in Science and Religion" he noted that both science and religion combined both discovery and exploration of external reality and the invention and construction of theories in human minds. Barbour identified Critical Realism as a philosophy to acknowledge "both the creativity of man's mind and the existence of patterns in events not created by man's mind" (Barbour, 1974, p. 37). The key insight in Barbour's critical realist approach was the balanced relation it formed between the internal world of the mind and the external world of events forming a bridge between skepticism and certainty.

The critical realism described by Barbour, Polkinghorne, and others integrated two seemingly opposite ways of knowing: reason and revelation. Speaking of critical realism's epistemology, Polkinghorne said,

"Science does not have a privileged route of access to knowledge through some superior 'scientific method', uniquely its own possession; theology does not have a privileged route of access to knowledge through some ineffable source of unquestionable 'revelation', uniquely its own possession." (1998, p. 20)

Rather, Polkinghorne argued that critical realism integrated human attempts to understand the physical world they transcend, with attempts to understand the mysteries of a God who transcends them. Mankind was positioned between knowing nothing about the physical world and knowing objectively and certainly. Polkinghorne defined a critical realist philosophy of knowing as follows:

"It [critical realism] is a realist position because it claims the attainment of increasingly verisimilitudinous knowledge of the nature of the physical world. It is critical realist position because that knowledge is not directly obtained by looking at what is going on, but it requires a subtle and creative interaction between interpretation and experiment." (1998, p. 17)

On the one hand, critical realism embraces a knowable external reality and rejects the constructivist idea that reality is "only" an invention

or construction of people's minds. John Polkinghorne said that "far from behaving like epistemological clay in our pattern-seeking hands ... the physical world frequently proves surprising, resisting our expectations..." (2005, p. 4). On the other hand, critical realism embraces personal interpretive viewpoints and rejects the enlightenment ideal of a simple objective understanding of reality, what Ian Barbour called the 'naive realist' (1974, p. 37). Critical realism accounts for the fact that each individual person has a unique perspective on reality. You see it this way. I see it that way. Both you and I may be right in some meaningful way. But the reality each of us observes is fixed. Either it is, or is not, the way either of us see it. A nuance of intellectual life is the distinction between either/or thinking and both/and thinking. Critical realism integrates these two. It accounts for an either/or reality that includes many both/and individual perspectives that can be right without being contradictory. Polanyi would say that we can be personal without being subjective (Polanyi, 1958).

Physicist John Polkinghorne claimed that critical realism was a philosophical position based on the broad experience of the scientific community rather than an abstract reasoning, saying, "This basis in experience is why it [critical realism] is the position adopted, consciously or unconsciously, by the overwhelming majority of scientists, despite the criticism leveled at it by some of their philosophical colleagues." (1998, p. 17) Critical realism was practice oriented. It was also supportive of discourse communities. Theologian Francis Schaffer held that meaning could be shared universally enough among individuals to be able to make truth claims about God and nature, saying, "We do not have to choose between these two extremes (skepticism or certainty), either in language or epistemology. We can know truly without knowing exhaustively" (Schaffer, 1972, p. 74). Leading contemporary theologian N. T. Wright described his critical realist-based epistemology this way:

"...I propose a form of *critical realism*. This is a way of describing the process of 'knowing' that acknowledges the *reality of the thing known, as something other than the knower* (hence 'realism'), while also fully acknowledging that the only access we have to this reality lies along the spiraling path of *appropriate dialogue or conversation*

between the knower and the thing known (hence 'critical'). (1992, p. 37)

Wright's definition emphasizes 'dialogue or conversation,' a conceptual cousin of the discourse favored by epistemological constructivists, yet without devolving into subjective deconstruction of reality. Through communication the personal experiences of one knower can be compared with experiences of other knowers. Through a combination of this dialogue of knowers, and physical reality, knowledge can be verified or falsified to a reasonable degree. Thus critical realism bridges the divide between not only science and theology but between subjectivists and objectivists as well.

The use of the integrative philosophy of critical realism by leading scientists and theologians validates that integration of diverse even opposing disciplinary perspectives is both possible and productive. More to the point of this paper, I argue here that critical realism, as an integrative philosophy, based in practice, supporting community discourse to form new knowledge, provides a useful foundation for an epistemology for design. But before I get to the proposed design epistemology, one brief qualification is needed to avoid confusion about integration, followed by a sketch from Michael Polanyi of how knowledge is in fact formed.

SYNTHESIS

Integration of ideas may sound attractive, but there is an inherent danger in it. It became popular in the last century to resolve the differing views of reality by simply including all sides. That is not what I am proposing here. Polkinghorne wrote that,

"...postmodernism has suggested that instead of truth about reality, we have to settle for a portfolio of opinions expressing personal or societal points of view. Though there may appear to be conflicts between the different perspectives proposed, it is said that there is no real competition because, in fact, there is not actually anything to contend about. All points of view can claim equal authenticity, since none is constrained by an independently accessible reality. The story goes that intellectual life is strictly à la carte." (Polkinghorne, 2005, p. 2)

Critical realism may sound familiar in postmodernist ears because it sounds inclusive: reality à la carte. However, critical realism is integrative, not inclusive

in the postmodern sense, because it accounts for both either/or and both/and thinking without blurring the distinction between the two.

PERSONAL KNOWLEDGE

The philosophy of critical realism found a home in the epistemology of personal knowledge developed by Michael Polanyi in his books *Personal Knowledge* (1958) and *The Tacit Dimension* (1966). Like many others since Plato, Polanyi affirmed that knowing is a process of integrating particulars into universals (the theme of this conference). His unique insight was in how the integration happens. He said that particulars cannot be integrated into new concepts so long as the particulars remain the focus of attention.

PROCESS USING SUBSIDIARY AND FOCAL AWARENESS

To integrate particulars into universals Polanyi theorized a process that utilizes two kinds of awareness: one sensed and dwelt, and the other conscious and aware. Polanyi called one Subsidiary Awareness: the particular tools or content we use to think with, and the other Focal Awareness: the conscious object of our thinking/awareness. As we think, the subsidiary tools of thought are internalized out of consciousness while they are being used to think with, perhaps to solve a problem. Polanyi pointed out that as soon as we focus on individual features we lose the power to find connections in the whole. For example, if we focus attention only on individual words we can never comprehend the meaning of a whole text. Subsidiary ideas are more than puzzle pieces, they are the clues, the elements, the raw material that make attending to a focal target possible (Mitchell, p. 71). Polanyi says:

"For such an act relies on interiorizing particulars to which we are not attending and which, therefore, we may not be able to specify, and relies further on our attending from these unspecifiable particulars to a comprehensive entity connecting them in a way we cannot define." (1983, p. 24)

Polanyi scholar Mark Mitchell says, "The integration of these two kinds of awareness occurs in any act of knowing" (Mitchell, 2006, p. 71).

TACIT AND EXPLICIT KNOWLEDGE

A key part of the Polanyi quote above is his statement, "...we may not be able to specify..."

Because Polanyi shows that part of the process of knowing is not completely conscious he therefore maintains that we may form two kinds of knowledge as a result: tacit and explicit. Explicit knowledge is that we are aware of and consciously know. Tacit knowledge is more elusive. Polanyi references our ability to recognize different faces, to master a skill such as playing an instrument, or to ride a bike all without being able to tell how we know how to do these things as examples of tacit knowledge. Polanyi said, "We know more than we can tell" (1983, p. 4). More relevant to design, Polanyi also cites perception as an act of tacit knowing in that we are not aware of the physical sensations themselves, but only of the external object toward which our senses point us: you are not aware of seeing this text, you are reading it. When reading this article you attend not to each word but to the thoughts produced by the words taken together. You 'know' the meaning of individual words only in so far as you rely on them to arrive at the overall meaning of the text. If you focus only on individual words (out of sequence) the meaning eludes you. Since you are not attending to (focusing on) the words themselves you may not even remember them but if the article is proving to be meaningful to you then you will be explicitly aware of your impression of it. This is the functional relationship between tacit and explicit knowledge.

CONCLUSION

I see Polanyi's description of thought processes: subsidiary and focal, and the kinds of knowledge that grow from them: tacit and explicit, relating closely to words designers use to describe creative thinking: inspiration, insight, and intuition. The sudden experience of converting tacit to explicit knowledge may be described as flashes of insight or inspiration. Design actions based on tacit knowledge may explain what designers call intuition. Polanyi's concepts fit with design experience and provide good insight for a design epistemology.

EPISTEMOLOGY AND DESIGN

Sharon Poggenpohl has described design as a discipline that is emerging from a craft. (Poggenpohl, 2009) Various authors have pointed out that design, coming from a craft background, is primarily practice-based producing procedural or

know-how knowledge rather than declarative or know-that knowledge. Before articulating an epistemology for design, it's important to briefly unpack in greater detail what procedural knowledge is like in design, who the persons are that do design thinking, and what kind of design it all concerns. Rather than rely on contemporary viewpoints that can too heavily reflect current trends, I have gone back to the most ancient text I am aware of that describes a designer: the fifteenth century B.C. Hebrew Pentateuch, the book of the Exodus:

Then Moses said to the sons of Israel, "See, the LORD has called by name Bezalel the son of Uri, the son of Hur, of the tribe of Judah. And He has filled him with the Spirit of God, in wisdom, in understanding and in knowledge and in all craftsmanship; to make designs for working in gold and in silver and in bronze, and in the cutting of stones for settings and in the carving of wood, so as to perform in every inventive work. He also has put in his heart to teach, both he and Oholiab, the son of Ahisamach, of the tribe of Dan. He has filled them with skill to perform every work of an engraver and of a designer and of an embroiderer, in blue and in purple *and* in scarlet *material*, and in fine linen, and of a weaver, as performers of every work and makers of designs. Ex 35:30-35 (NASB, 1995)

This text uses four key words related to designers Bezalel and Oholiab: wisdom, understanding, knowledge, and craftsmanship. Based on the Hebrew definitions, I understand these words to describe different phases in a design knowing process.

To start at the elemental level, I'll add to the Exodus description a word in abundant contemporary use: 'data.' I'll define data as a form of knowing where one is aware of individual facts of reality. EXAMPLE: Dump a library card catalog on a table and you have data.

The third word from the Hebrew text is the word DAATH: 'knowledge.' The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament (TWOT) (Archer, Harris, & Waltke, 2003) defines DAATH as: "knowledge gained by the senses. ... In certain contexts it means 'to distinguish.' ... A child cannot distinguish between the left and right hands." Knowledge is a form of knowing where one distinguishes between shared and diverse data features, thus assembling data into categories. EXAMPLE: Dump a library card catalog on a table and

you have data. Organize those cards into categories and thereby come to a new concept of a category that is greater than the mere sum of the individual data ‘cards,’ and you have formed knowledge.

The second word is ‘understanding.’ The Hebrew is *TEBUNAH* / *TEVUNA*, again from *TWOT*: “The background idea of the verb is ‘to discern,’ and this lies behind the derivative nouns and the close relation derived from the substantive ‘bin’ ... from which comes the preposition ‘between.’ ... The verb refers to knowledge that is superior to the mere gathering of data. It is necessary to know how to use knowledge one possesses.” Understanding is a form of knowing where the implications of knowledge are perceived. It comes from making connections between kinds of things, discerning their overall character, and coming to conclusions as to their nature, usefulness, and/or quality. It involves discernment, knowing the meaningful difference between one kind of thing and another. **EXAMPLE:** Knowing that ‘A’ is an army is knowledge. Knowing that ‘A’ is an opposing army of ‘B’ and that war is a likely result of their interaction is understanding.

The first word in the group is *HOKMA* / *CHOKMAH*, ‘wisdom.’ Again from *TWOT*: “The essential idea of *HKM* represents a manner of thinking and attitude concerning life’s experiences including matters of general interest and basic morality. These concerns relate to prudence in secular affairs, skills in the arts, moral sensitivity, and experience in the ways of the Lord.” Wisdom is an advanced form of knowing: “Wisdom is supreme; therefore get wisdom.” Proverbs 4:7a (NASB) is carved over the entry to one of the oldest buildings on the campus where I teach. Wisdom flowers when knowledge and understanding interact with reality and change the capacity and the character, “skill” and “prudence,” of the knower. Wisdom grows as a result of experience: applying understanding appropriately to circumstances, observing the results and reflecting upon them to form new knowledge. Previously theoretical information is reconnected to reality in a functional way. Wisdom is built on knowledge and understanding. **EXAMPLE:** A wise leader, knowing army A and B are facing off, and having experienced many wars and participated in war councils as both government minister and army general and having gained understanding of conflict,

power and peace, this wise leader is in a position to negotiate peace.

The epistemology of Polanyi as described above may lead one to think only of integrating data into knowledge. But from the word definitions above, it’s clear that designers’ procedural knowledge includes other kinds of knowing: understanding and wisdom. These may show themselves in particular level of work called craftsmanship. In addition to affecting the product of thought, the application of understanding to practice physically changes the knower, making the person a craftsman. I propose that an epistemology for design must account for these other levels of knowing, not just descriptive knowledge from data, but rich, varied kinds of procedural knowledge from practice.

While I assert that design knowing moves beyond converting data to knowledge to gaining understanding and wisdom, it would be a mistake to think of this process as too linear, too reasoned. Design knowledge does not grow in isolation, but different lessons may be at different levels of development at the same time, influencing each other and informing each other both explicitly and tacitly. New knowledge in one area can contribute to sudden understanding in another area, and so on. Design knowledge grows in and out of sequence and simultaneously. However, following the definitions above, for any given area the highest level of wisdom cannot be attained without first progressing from knowledge through understanding to application.

The Exodus text exposes another feature of design knowing that needs unpacking. It describes how specific individuals, Bazalel and Oholiab, are given a special calling as designers. This is in contrast to Krippendorf who has noted, and common experience affirms, that everyone is a designer. Clearly there are designers, and then there are designers of special ability.

This points toward the issue of not only who a designer is, but what design is. A widely adopted definition of design is that offered by Herb Simon: the process of changing existing states to preferred ones. Everyone does this. In defining a design epistemology we need to consider which design the epistemology purports to describe: what everyone does or what specialists do. To study the practice of design, Cross, Simon and others have variously

studied designers, engineers, architects, and design students. This is a more inclusive definition of design, toward the 'every person designs' model. Yet the thinking processes of designers and engineers are decidedly different, as UC colleague Mary Beth Privitera has explored and described her analysis of teams of designers and engineers working on medical device design. (Privitera, 2006) A more specialist definition of design would focus on professional designers working in design consultancies or corporations. To form a distinctive design epistemology it's reasonable that a focus on the most advanced, or sophisticated, or narrow definition of design will produce more definitive results, rather than to develop using a broad, or inclusive, or universal design definition. However, while focusing narrowly on professional designers it's also reasonable to look broadly at all design specializations: fashion, graphic, and interior design, not just focus for example on industrial designers as has often been the case (Cross and Krippendorff for example have a product design focus). The current lack of consensus on design epistemology could be evidence of previous authors focusing too broadly on the one hand: including engineers, and too narrowly on the other: limiting to industrial design.

To sketch an epistemology for designers I will focus narrowly at the level of professional design consultant aiming for a distinct definition. I will assume that everyday designers will utilize similar thinking processes but at a lower level in quality and/or quantity of processes and techniques. I will focus on design as a transformative practice resulting in products intended to institute change. The design products can be intangible strategies, services, communications or physical objects. And I will take design knowledge to be inherently procedural that includes understanding, wisdom and skilled craft.

DESIGN EPISTEMOLOGY: REASON + REVELATION

The dichotomy between reason and revelation stated by E. O. Wilson at the start of this paper could suggest irreconcilable differences, but the foregoing discussion about integration suggest that that a continuum with extremes may be a more appropriate conception. Working from this, I propose an integrative design epistemology based on critical

realism and personal knowledge called Reason + Revelation (R+R): "Reason" because explicit, rational, and analytical, thinking processes are used; "Revelation" because tacit-to-explicit, inspired, non-linear, divergent, and integrative thinking processes are embraced; "+" because integrating both Reason + Revelation equally together encompasses divergent thinking mechanisms such as focused analysis and sudden insight in a balanced way, with neither taking precedence. The proposed name uses definitions from the Oxford on-line dictionary: reason: the power of the mind to think, + revelation: a surprising and previously unknown fact, esp. one that is made known in a dramatic way.

Reason + Revelation is an integrated approach to design knowing wedding logic with intuition, and reason with revelation. I use logic and intuition not to imply that intuition is illogical, but to describe two thinking processes related to Polanyi's subsidiary and focal awareness while reason and revelation describe two ways these thinking processes connect to reality. In R+R intuition is not a-logical, nor is it counter logical, but intuition is more accurately described as the sudden emergence of tacit knowing processes to explicit awareness. R+R holds that intuition and logic are equally logical and valid knowing processes that are fully integrated in the mechanics of thought. Similarly, in R+R reason and revelation describe two routes to reality, with reason focusing on the individual mind's using logic to project toward what is perceived and revelation focusing on knowing that comes from outside of self. It is a difference in direction: one from inside out; the other from outside in. Faith and belief are key parts of the vocabulary of revelation, these relate to Polanyi's 'commitment,' and his suggestion that without commitment there is no knowing. Revelation reflects the communal aspect of knowing, whether the knowledge comes from a deity or a community. Though Krippendorff may take issue with the comparison, revelation accounts for second-order understanding where designers gain understanding from user communities. Revelation is not a less logical but a less individualistic way of connecting with reality. Revelation thus describes the human discovery of truth particularly through interaction in community. Reason connects the mind with the external, physical world through analyzing data. R+R

provides epistemological foundation for Cross' "broad and catholic approach" (Cross, 2007, p. 123) encompassing both Schön's constructivist reflective practice and Simon's positivist science of the artificial. R+R does this by redefining science away from objectivism and rationalism along the lines described in critical realism.

R+R as I conceive it has at least three features that make it distinctive for design:

1. equivalence of analytical + creative thinking,
2. reliance on visual tools for thinking and for expressing thought,
3. practice-based.

1. ANALYTICAL + CREATIVE THINKING

R+R in design utilizes explicit, reasoned, analytical, focally aware thinking processes in near equal balance with tacit, revelatory, intuitional, subsidiary thinking. R+R is how designers simultaneously consider multiple factors: physical, sociological, and commercial for example, in tacit and subsidiary processes during creative problem solving. R+R doesn't only balance these processes simultaneously and in equal measure, but it also shifts constantly and instantly from tacit to explicit, creative to analytical thinking during the design process in a flow between problem analysis (analytical) to solution creation (creative) and back to solution evaluation (analytical). Again, it is too literal to think of these locked always in linear sequence. R+R is an iterative and on-going flow between analysis and inspiration. Using R+R designers are free to say, "It came to me in a flash when I was taking a shower," or "after analyzing the problem I was inspired by it to..."

2. RELIANCE ON VISUAL TOOLS FOR THINKING AND EXPRESSING THOUGHT

Analytical and creative thinking may seem like thought processes while visual processes are merely mechanical tools to express thought, but to make this assumption is to misunderstand visual thinking. Research has demonstrated that different verbal and non-verbal/visual neurological processes affect learning. (Mayer, 2001) Kosslyn and others have demonstrated how visual form is used in thinking and problem solving quite apart from words. (Kosslyn, Thompson, & Ganis, 2006) Visual perception is itself

a thinking process, part of which is tacit and part of which is explicit. Part of our visual perception that feeds and supports visual thinking is preattentive, operating largely independent of our conscious thought (Treisman, 1985), like tacit knowledge. Visual perception is also explicit, as evidenced in visual search and attentive processes that control what we see. (Ware, 2004) R+R encompasses visual thinking as typified by mental imaging and visual perceptual processes. R+R supports not only visual thinking but also visual communication. Drawing is evidence of visual thinking (Arnheim, 1969). Drawing is the non-verbal conversion of thought to image thus allowing for knowledge to remain tacit while still being expressed. R+R supports both drawing's embodiment of tacit thought: tacit to explicit, and representational visualization's stimulation of further creative thought: explicit to tacit. Designers may say, "it just looks right..." or "I like the look of that, but what about this..."

3. PRACTICE BASED KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT

R+R in design grows in-situ, through practice. Knowledge flow is from praxis to theory and back to practice: know how - know that - know how. I described in detail above how practice-based knowledge fits design as craft and legitimizes concepts such as wisdom and craftsmanship as forms of knowing in design. Current design pedagogy embodies practice-based R+R as students learn first through doing mock projects and then by subsequently reflecting on their experience. Poggenpohl and others have called for advancing disciplinary knowledge beyond craft. R+R provides conceptual support for this by defining it as a need for more effective and overt conversion of tacit to explicit knowledge. R+R also outlines how to do research to facilitate this conversion. R+R outlines how to apply explicit scientific knowledge of perception for example, to help designers convert their tacit understanding of visual form like the functional interaction of hue, into explicit principles for design practice. R+R outlines how to take this new knowledge of visual form based on perception, apply it in a design exercise and laboratory experiment, thus moving from know that, to know how, to know that, and eventually to know how as principles are later applied to other design work.

Other features that may be considered as key in an epistemology for design, such as the role of iteration, or the creative stimulus provided by a host of practical realities from physics to users, but as a starting point I propose these three as essentials.

VALIDATION

R+R may sound reasonable, and have a respectable foundation, but is it descriptive of design? Any epistemology is, by nature, speculative and philosophical. A model of thinking cannot, without circular reasoning, use its reasoning method to prove that it is the true method of knowing. Theologian and critical realist N. T. Wright in his chapter "Knowledge: Problems and Varieties" suggested a way out of this,

"All epistemologies have to be, themselves, argued as hypotheses: they are tested not by their coherence with a fixed point agreed in advance, but (like other hypotheses, in fact) by their simplicity and by their ability to make sense of a wide scope of experiences and events." (1992, pp. 45-46)

Wright proposes that knowledge can be validated in practice through application of the theory to diverse experiences with analysis of results. The criteria he proposes are: simplicity and inclusive scope. First I'll suggest four simple but inclusive validation criteria for design, then briefly apply R+R to two of those.

VALIDATION: APPLYING R+R TO DESIGN

Following Wright's suggestion that the criteria for judging a design epistemology is that it should simply explain a 'wide scope of experiences and events,' I suggest the following criteria for evaluating R+R as a proposed epistemology for design:

because the working of human minds appears to be consistent across recorded history, a design epistemology should help explain design history, and because cultural contexts change over time, a design epistemology should illuminate the various design arguments in every age;
because design is a practice, a design epistemology should be useful in practice, and because design practice is both a noun and a verb, a design epistemology should enable both design thinking and design making;
because design desires to be a discipline, its epistemology should be universal across disciplinary specialties yet unique to the

discipline of design, and because a design discipline is also an academic enterprise, a design epistemology should support design research and education;
because design is aimed at 'converting existing states into preferred ones', a design epistemology should support an ethical dimension distinguishing what is, from what ought to be.

These four cover key areas that define a discipline:

1. history, theory, criticism;
2. praxis, process, product;
3. education, research, theory formation;
4. ethics.

Without making exhaustive validation beyond this paper's and my personal scope, I'll describe how I have seen that R+R fits my own design practice (#2), and my teaching and research (#3).

DESIGN PRACTICE

My design practice and that of others relies heavily on visual embodiment of ideas. Visualization is the language of design. Other disciplines rely on words and mathematics to embody thought. These predefined systems for embodying thought are more structured than drawing. Designers rely more on the unstructured physical act of drawing as a bridge from visual thought to physical manifestation, as described above. Drawing's free flow from thought to expression could help explain why design thinking is considered creative and why design practitioners are routinely called upon to stimulate innovation. Design practice relies on representational and symbolic visual form not only to communicate, but to think. Designers sketch and doodle to work out problems. How thought is embodied is evidence of the thought processes: epistemology.

I'm a professional designer. I have observed in myself since earliest childhood that I have an unusual visual memory, being able to remember effortlessly what I've seen, in detail, and the circumstance of seeing it. I can recall much more easily the page and place on the page of a striking photograph and I can remember person's name. My visual knowledge is largely tacit. I don't try to do it, or know how I do it. I think in images, analyze data in images, and express ideas in images. It may be that my distinctive knowing comes in large part from my constant movement from thought world to physical world and back, facilitated by visual language which is non-linear and can be highly abstract or highly literal.

Design Research

I find that R+R makes specific and direct contribution to my current design research focus: forming new knowledge by integration of particulars into universals, and thus to the theme of this design research conference: 'Unity and Diversity'.

Design research has succeeded in debating the definition of design research without coming to a consensus. Erlhoff and Marshall (eds.) describe design research as being 'vaguely defined' (Erlhoff & Marshall, 2008, p. 332). They go on to summarize a mixture of research methods used in design. R+R provides a foundation for a distinctive design approach to research that integrates qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative research, using a subjectivist approaches from an intuitionist-pluralist worldview, analyzes cultural, anthropological, emotional and psychological data in order to discover or validate what is. Quantitative research uses an objectivist approach derived from a logical-positivist perspective to discover or validate what is (Friedman & Wyatt, 2006). R+R supports integration of these in mixed methods research.

Openly mixing methods is a relatively new practice (Creswell & Clark, 2007) that I have used in design research studies, including one reported on elsewhere at this conference. A mixed-methods design research study may first collect input from open-ended questions or observational studies (qualitative); then design a survey to validate and further explore the initial findings (quantitative). To typical analytical research methods design freely adds visualization, whether scientific data or mood boards. R+R provides an epistemological foundation integrating mixed methods.

CONCLUSION

To form a distinctive design epistemology such as R+R, based on an existing philosophy such as critical realism, and an epistemological theory such as personal knowledge, at least two things should be demonstrated: that these fit design, and that an epistemology for design adds something particular to them. The sketch of R+R demonstrates both similarity with its antecedents and the addition of something peculiar to them. As said at the start of this paper, an epistemological foundation is essential if a discipline is to build a distinctive superstructure

of research, education, and practice. It remains to be seen whether Reason + Revelation can be further validated so as to answer the epistemological question that will help define design as a discipline.

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